

ANALYTICAL MODELLING AND LIFING OF CONTINUOUS FIBRE REINFORCED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Room temperature fatigue crack growth in single edge notched specimens of Ti-6Al-4V alloy with SCS-6 cross-ply reinforcement has been studied and characterised on the basis of applied stress intensity factor ranges. Matrix crack growth and acoustic emissions were monitored continuously throughout each test. The divergence between the apparent and effective stress intensity ranges was then modelled as a function of crack length by assuming that the fibres in the crack wake act as linear springs. By comparing model predictions and crack growth data, values for the spring/crack modulus, k/E , were deduced empirically and then used to predict matrix crack growth. A stochastic model of fibre damage was used to model the effect of fibre failures on crack growth resistance and to predict possible transitions from non-catastrophic to catastrophic behaviour.

1. INTRODUCTION

Titanium metal matrix composites (Ti-MMCs) are advanced structural materials which are under consideration as replacement materials for some conventional monolithic titanium alloy components in the next generation of gas turbine aeroengines. It is envisaged that the high cost of implementing these new materials will be offset by improvements in overall engine performance made possible because of their superior high temperature properties and high strength-to-weight and stiffness-to-weight ratios. Several critical lifing issues must be resolved, however, before Ti-MMCs can be used in components. It has been demonstrated that fatigue cracks will quite readily initiate and grow in the matrix at cyclic loads that are a small percentage of the static strength of the material [1]. It has also been shown that partly debonded but nevertheless intact fibres bridging the wake of such a fatigue crack will inhibit the opening and closing of the crack tip, thus retarding, and sometimes even arresting, the growth of the crack [2].

Many crack bridging models [3-6] have been developed which explain the phenomena observed in fatigue, and techniques for calculating crack tip stress intensity factors under such circumstances have been widely published [7-9]. Thus far, however, comparative experimental and theoretical studies of the fatigue of Ti-MMCs have concentrated on the literal application of the most popular micromechanical models. It has also been argued [10] that such micromodels can never be empirically verified and, furthermore, are not necessary in order for universal predictions to be made. In principle, the interaction between matrix and fibres may be described by a single function relating the fibre stress to the matrix crack opening displacement, and it should be possible to recognise this function as an engineering property. Theoretically, the validation of such a function merely requires a consistent agreement between predictions of matrix (and fibre) damage and experimental data *from different crack growth regimes*.

This paper compares the predictions of one such theoretical study, in which the force-displacement function is derived by semi-empirical means, with previously obtained data for crack growth in notched Ti-MMC cross-ply laminates [11]. This material is considered as a

"model system" for the purposes of comparative studies, because it possesses several desirable features:

- (1) single dominant mode I crack growth is almost guaranteed due to the cross-ply fibre architecture, thus facilitating the interpretation of crack growth data,
- (2) fibre failures are clearly and distinctly identified by acoustic emission monitoring, an extra degree of freedom with which to explore the effects of volume fraction and fibre architecture at some later date by comparing model predictions with test results for unidirectionally reinforced material.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Figure 1. Schematic diagram showing the fibre architecture of $(0/90)_{2s}$ and $(90/0)_{2s}$ single edge notched bend (SEN) specimens. These two lay-ups are obtained from a single symmetrical 8-ply laminate of Ti-6-4 foils and SCS-6 fibres by cutting and notching in mutually perpendicular orientations. The designation refers to the stacking order of plies through the testpiece thickness - $(0/90)$ means that the first near-surface ply contains bridging (0°) fibres, in $(90/0)$ specimens these bridging (0°) fibres are found in the second, sub-surface ply.

2.1. Materials Preparation

The material was manufactured by the foil-fibre-foil route, using foils of conventional Ti-6Al-4V alloy, continuously reinforced with approximately 35% volume fraction of Textron SCS-6 fibres. These fibres are made from $140\mu\text{m}$ diameter silicon carbide, with alternating coating layers of SiC and carbon, and which allow the fibre to debond easily from the matrix. The fibres and foils were layed up into an 8-ply symmetrical $(0/90)$ laminate approximately 2mm in thickness. From this panel, SEN specimens 75mm in length and 4mm in width were cut by electro-discharge machining (EDM) in two mutually perpendicular orientations. In this way $[0/90]_{2s}$ and $[90/0]_{2s}$ laminates were obtained for testing (figure 1). All notches were cut to a through-thickness depth of approximately 1mm using either a slow diamond saw or EDM.

2.2. Fatigue crack growth tests and acoustic emission monitoring

The fatigue testing was performed in three point bending on an ESH servo-hydraulic testing machine, at room temperature and cycling at a frequency of 0.5Hz. Each test was carried out at a constant load range and at a R ratio (the ratio of minimum to maximum stress applied over the fatigue cycle) of 0.1. The load ranges were selected to give initial ΔK values at the notch of 12, 14, 16 and 18 $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ for the $[0/90]_{2s}$ lay-ups, and of 12 and 18 $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ for the $[90/0]_{2s}$ lay-ups. Crack growth was continuously monitored using a dc potential drop technique. Acoustic emissions were monitored using a Fuji Ceramics M53 300kHz resonant piezoelectric transducer glued to the specimen near the notch [12]. The AE signals were amplified by a pre-amplifier with a 26dB gain, and were then analysed by a PAC LOCAN Jr after a further 20dB gain. Following each test, the fracture surfaces were examined using a scanning electron microscope to assess the consistency of fibre distribution and to estimate pull-out lengths.

3. ANALYTICAL MODELLING

3.1. Matrix Crack Growth Analysis

Matrix crack growth rates were calculated as a function of the cyclic matrix stress intensity factor using an unorthodox formulation which incorporates all three regimes of crack growth (but which approximates to the Paris law for intermediate values of crack growth rate):

$$\frac{da}{dN} = A \left[\frac{\Delta K_m^2 - \Delta K_0^2}{1 - (\Delta K_m / \Delta K_c)^2} \right] \dots (1)$$

where A is a constant; ΔK_m , ΔK_0 and ΔK_c are, respectively, the matrix, threshold, and critical cyclic stress intensity factors. A fair representation of the matrix crack growth data was found when $\Delta K_0 = 3.8 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$, $\Delta K_c = 36 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$, and $A = 1.2 \text{ E-}7 \text{ mm/cycle}$. The composite crack growth rates near the notch (fig. 4) appear to converge with the matrix crack growth rates, hence $\Delta K_m = \Delta K_{applied}$. At this point, $\Delta K_{tip} = \Delta K_{applied}$, where ΔK_{tip} is the composite cyclic stress intensity factor. Hence it also seems reasonable to assume that $\Delta K_m = \Delta K_{tip}$. The same assumption has been made previously in a similar work on cross-ply laminates [13]. The matrix stress intensity factor is therefore given by:

$$\Delta K_m(a) = \int_0^a \Delta \sigma(x) \cdot m(a, x) dx \dots (2)$$

where $\Delta \sigma(x)$ is the unknown crack-line stress distribution and $m(a, x)$ is the weight function for a crack of length a (see appendix A). The opening displacement of the crack surfaces, $\Delta u(x)$ is determined using Castigliano's theorem (as outlined in [14]), whereby:

$$\Delta u(x) = \frac{1}{E'} \int_x^a \Delta K_m(a') \cdot m(a', x) da' \dots (3)$$

E' , which is sometimes referred to as the orthotropic composite modulus, is an elastic constant. The crack-line stress distribution for an SENB specimen is then given by:

$$\Delta \sigma(x) = \Delta \sigma_{surface} [1 - (2x/W)] - p[\Delta u(x)] \dots (4)$$

where W is the specimen width, $\Delta \sigma_{surface}$ is the cyclic stress range at the specimen edge and $p(u)$ is the the force-displacement function (equal to zero for $x < a_0$ where a_0 is the notch depth). By varying x over the entire crack length and iterating Eqn. (4) to maintain self-consistency, the matrix crack growth rates can be calculated from the substitution of Eqn.(2) into Eqn.(1). The solution therefore depends entirely upon the form of $p(u)$. According to shear lag model predictions this function has a quadratic form, and corresponds to fibres coupled to a matrix by friction. Other contemporary crack bridging models exist in the literature which use linear functions (fibres acting as springs with no hysteresis) or functions with a peak and a tail (corresponding to a distribution of critical crack opening displacements for fibre failure and possible contributions after pull-out). In general the initial increasing part of $p(u)$ can be characterised by the relation:

$$|p - p_r| = \beta |u - u_r|^\alpha \dots (5)$$

where p_r and u_r are the values obtained at the last point of load reversal, whilst α and β are constants (for the shear lag model, $\alpha = 1/2$ and the friction stress is proportional to β^2). One theoretical result arising from the general power law bridging approach is the prediction of a characteristic "bridging length scale" in fatigue, loosely analogous to an attenuation length for a travelling wave. If correct, then the shear lag model predicts that the bridging length scale increases with applied stress amplitude. On the other hand if it is incorrect, using the friction stress as a fitting parameter for crack growth data will tend to suggest that the friction stress either increases (if $0 < \alpha < 1/2$) or decreases (for $1 \geq \alpha > 1/2$) as a function of applied load.

In this respect, previous work seeking to validate shear lag formulations should be an excellent guide to a putative form of Eqn 5. A brief survey of such studies e.g. [3, 4, 6] reveals that the friction stress is often quoted as increasing with respect to the applied stress range, which suggests that α is high. It was therefore assumed for this model that unfailed fibres act as a collection of linear springs such that:

$$\Delta p(x) = k \cdot \Delta u(x) \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

where k is the spring constant. If we assume that the fibres strain linearly over the slip length, a rough estimate of k is quite simply fE_f/l_s , the ratio of fibre modulus to slip length multiplied by the fibre volume fraction, f . The parameter governing the bridging length scale in fatigue then becomes k/E' , the "spring/crack" modulus, which was used to fit crack growth data. This parameter has the units of reciprocal length, such that the bridging length scale (or attenuation length) decreases as k/E' increases. From estimates based on pull-out lengths, k/E' is of the order of 1 mm^{-1} (based on a slip length estimate of $500\mu\text{m}$).

3.2. Modelling Fibre Damage

One important characteristic of MMCs which have a relatively ductile matrix reinforced by strong brittle fibres is that the crack growth resistance tends to be dependent on the interfacial properties. Both fracture toughness and crack growth resistance will be controlled primarily by the failure of brittle fibres. In particular we focus on the behaviour of bridged cracks i.e. with intact fibres behind the growing crack tip. In such circumstances a high interfacial strength and short debond length may be beneficial *provided that the fibres do not fail*. Under relatively high applied loads a weaker interfacial bond may be preferable. Hence the value of the spring constant will have a profound effect on the resistance of the composite to fibre damage.

Since in reality the fibres will have not one but a distribution of values for k (corresponding to a range of debond lengths), they will reach the critical stress for fracture over a range of crack opening displacements. Hence a simple Weibull type distribution can be invoked to represent the peak and tail of $p(u)$ for high values of u :

$$p(x) = k \cdot \Delta u(x) \exp \left[- (a - a_0)^n \left(\frac{k \cdot \Delta u(x)}{f(1-R)\sigma_n} \right)^m \right] \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

where σ_n is a normalising parameter of no physical significance (which in the limit for high values of m becomes the single valued fracture stress for a reference volume of fibres), m is a shape parameter and n determines the sensitivity of the fibre strength with respect to the volume of material sampled in the crack wake. The tendency for fibres to fail can be expressed in a semi-quantitative manner by averaging $[p(x)/k \cdot \Delta u(x)]$ over all x and then multiplying by the estimated number of bridging fibres, giving an effective fibre damage accumulation parameter.. For the cases where considerable numbers of fibres fail prior to the end of the test, the parameters for Eqn. (7) were adjusted until good agreement was reached between the recorded number of fibre failures and the damage accumulation parameter. For cracks propagating in a non-catastrophic mode (very few or no fibre failures recorded), a high value of m was assumed giving rise to distinct stable and meta-stable solutions. Assuming a low value of m in this regime gives an overly conservative total life estimate, and is a consequence of representing *discrete* fibre damage by the present *continuum* model.

The meta-stable solution was obtained by assuming that the crack was fully bridged prior to the interaction of Eqn (4), whilst the stable solution was obtained by assuming that the crack was initially unbridged. At some critical crack length, the solutions were found to converge. Beyond this point, simulating fibre failures by incrementing the notch length can produce a discontinuous transition from a meta-stable to a stable solution. In other words, the impact of breaking a few fibres on the remaining bridging fibres can be very dramatic. Such results help to define the true defect and damage tolerance of the material in a regime where statistical analysis is not possible.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Fatigue crack growth resistance curves

Figure 2 shows how crack growth rates in the matrix increase with applied stress intensity range, ΔK_a for the unreinforced (monolithic) material [12] whilst in the case of the composite material the crack growth rates decrease as ΔK_a increases. This effect, commonly observed in constant load amplitude tests, arises because ΔK_a increases as the crack grows whilst ΔK_m decreases with crack length. Hence ΔK_a is relatively meaningless (except for the initial unbridged crack) and cannot be used to characterise matrix damage without a supplementary parameter which describes the effect of bridging length on crack growth resistance.

Figure 2. Crack growth resistance of cross-ply and unidirectionally reinforced Ti-6Al-4V alloy, relative to that of the unreinforced matrix foils. For all tests $R=0.1$, frequency = 0.5Hz, temperature = 25°C. The results of Eqn.(1) is shown for crack growth in the Paris and near-threshold regimes. (Monolithic and unidirectional test data courtesy of C. Barney.)

The problem, assuming that ΔK_a is known, can be expressed in the form:

$$\Delta K_m = \Delta K_a \frac{Y_{eff}(bridged)}{Y_0(unbridged)} \dots (8)$$

where Y_{eff} and Y_0 are respectively the effective bridged and unbridged compliance functions. For unfailed fibres acting as linear springs, Y_{eff}/Y_0 is a geometric factor, independent of applied load but dependent on the spring/crack modulus and the specimen geometry (fig. 3). The experimentally observed divergence between matrix and composite stress intensity range, $(\Delta K_a/\Delta K_m)$, see fig 2) can also be plotted in this form (fig.4). The divergence is plotted on a logarithmic scale to facilitate interpretation of the data. The experimental results clearly show that the bridging length scale neither increases nor decreases with respect to applied load, suggesting that the spring/crack model is essentially correct.

Table I shows the number of cycles to failure for various values of initial applied ΔK . Only matrix damage was observed at low values of ΔK , whilst from an initial ΔK of 16 - 18 MPa√m both matrix cracking and fibre fracture was observed. Figure 5 shows the elapsed number of cycles plotted against matrix crack length for three $[0/90]_{2s}$ specimens, together with the model crack growth predictions. Good agreement was found for the value of the spring/crack modulus despite the difference in initial applied stress intensity factor range.

Initial ΔK (MPa√m)	$[0/90]_{2s}$	$[90/0]_{2s}$
12	crack arrest	crack arrest
14	crack arrest	-
16	155 000	-
18	40 000	82 400
	25 400	25 000
		7 000

Table I. Number of cycles to failure for notched cross-ply laminates ($R=0.1, 0.5Hz$)

Figure 3. (above) Divergence between normal and effective compliance for various values of the "spring/crack" parameter k/E' (units of mm^{-1}). The divergence required for crack arrest at an initial ΔK of $12 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ is also shown (applied stress range = 205 MPa , $W=4\text{mm}$).

Figure 4. (right) Divergence calculated from crack growth data for various values of initial ΔK (units of $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$). The threshold crack length for an initial ΔK of 12 is nearly 2mm , suggesting a value for k/E' of $1-1.5 \text{ mm}^{-1}$.

Figure 5. (below) Matrix crack growth data for $[0/90]_{2s}$ specimens compared with model predictions, assuming no fibre failures.

Figure 6. Comparison of real data and continuum model predictions for repeat tests at an initial ΔK of 18 MPa \sqrt{m} . Predictions are for $m=2$, $n=0.5$, $\sigma_n=6000$ MPa. This corresponds to a peak fibre stress of 3.8 GPa for a reference volume of four fibres (one row). The parameter k/E' was used to fit the predictions to real data and has units of mm^{-1} . High values for k/E' promote fibre failure at shorter crack lengths and hence a reduced specimen life.

4.2. Fibre Damage Predictions

Repeat tests at an initial ΔK of 18 MPa \sqrt{m} show a large scatter in overall specimen life, an effect which can be simulated by varying the value of k/E' . The physical interpretation of this is that a few heavily loaded fibres may fail in the crack wake at relatively low crack opening displacements, leading to a reduced specimen life. In general, it was found that when a low value of m was specified the predicted crack growth rates were affected by simulated fibre damage before fibre failures were actually recorded in the test. Thus, in order to fit crack growth data a slightly higher value of k/E' was used than that required when no fibre damage was assumed. The predictions of fibre failure are consistent with the acoustic emission data (fig 6), despite the theoretical shortcomings of the present continuum model.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Crack growth in $[0/90]_{2s}$ and $[90/0]_{2s}$ Ti/SiC cross-ply laminates was modelled using fracture mechanics parameters combined with a stochastic model of fibre failures. Good evidence was found to suggest that, in fatigue, bridging fibres act as linear springs in the crack wake, contrary to the detailed predictions of shear lag theory. Conditions that promote crack arrest have been identified, and the influence of fibre failures on crack growth resistance has been illustrated. A combined spring/crack modulus, k/E' , was found to be the parameter governing both the bridging length scale and the onset of fibre fracture in fatigue.

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APPENDIX A

In Eqn. (2), the weight function $m(a,x)$ is given by [4, 16]:

$$m(a, x) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \frac{H(a, x)}{\sqrt{a-x}}$$

For a single edge crack of depth a in a specimen of width w :

$$H(a, x) = 1 + m_1 \frac{a-x}{a} + m_2 \frac{(a-x)^2}{a^2}$$

Where m_1 and m_2 are constants for a given value of (a/w) :

$$m_1 = 0.6147 + 17.1844 \frac{a^2}{w^2} + 8.7822 \frac{a^6}{w^6}$$

$$m_2 = 0.2502 + 3.2889 \frac{a^2}{w^2} + 70.0444 \frac{a^6}{w^6}$$